

Management of Indralupta with Pracchana- A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: *Indralupta* is one among the *shiro kapalagata roga*. According to Acharya Vagbhata, *pitta* along with *vata* invades the *romakoopa* causes hairfall. Vitiation of *Sleshma* along with *shonita* obstructs the channels of *Romakoopa* leading to the stoppage of regrowth of hair¹. This condition is known as *Indralupta*. *Indralupta* can be correlated with Alopecia areata in which there is a sudden hairfall that starts with one or more circular bald patches. In Ayurveda both *shodhana* and *shamana* treatments are prescribed for *Indralupta*. This is a case report of 25 year old male patient complaints of patchy hair loss and thinning of hair since 2 months.

Materials and Methods: The subject who approached Shalaky tantra opd of SDM Ayurveda hospital Udupi with symptoms of patchy hair loss and thinning of hair since 2 months was systematically reviewed and treatment modalities like *pracchana* and internally *Arogyavardhini rasa*, *Tiktaka kashaya*, *Saptamruta loha* and *Bhargava prokta rasayana* is advised.

Results: The subject showed marked improvement symptomatically.

Discussion: Ayurveda has great approach in curing the *Indralupta*. *Nidana parivarjana*, *shamanoushadis* and external applications are the main treatment modalities which can be concluded from this case report.

KEYWORDS: Indralupta, Alopecia areata, Pracchana

INTRODUCTION

Indralupta is one among the *shiro kapalagata roga*. According to Acharya Sushruta, *pitta* along with *vata* invades the *romakoopa* causes hairfall. Vitiation of *Sleshma* along with *shonita* obstructs the channels of *Romakoopa* leading to the stoppage of regrowth of hair. This condition is known as *Indralupta*. The main treatment suggested in *indralupta* is *raktamokshana* ie *siravyadha* or *pracchana*. *Indralupta* can be correlated with Alopecia areata in which there is a sudden hairfall that starts with one or more circular bald patches. It usually affects the head and face. Conservative management of this disorder include corticosteroid injections, corticosteroid topical application, oral corticosteroids which are having harmful side effects and not advisable for long term use.

CASE REPORT

A 25 year old male patient came to OPD of Shalaky Tantra department with the complaints of patchy hair loss and thinning of hair since 2 months. the onset was gradual and the site was occipital region. He was treated with corticosteroids and topical serum, but did not get much relief. So he approached our opd and was

diagnosed with indralupta and treatment was started. In personal history patient had weak appetite and constipated bowel.

Aharaja nidana:-intake of oily, spicy food, dairy products. Viharaja - exposure to dust.

On examination:-

- Inspection- patchy hair loss
- Site-occipital region
- Shape- vertically oval
- Scalp- dry scales
- **Laboratory investigations:-**
- Hb% - 14
- Bleeding time- 1 min 30 sec
- Clotting time- 3 min 20 sec

Treatment given

- Deepana pachana with chitrakadi vati²- 1 tid before food for 3 days
- Pracchana karma- (4 sittings, once in 7 days), followed by application of Icchabedi rasa.
- Arogyavardhini rasa- 2bd after food for 15 days
- Guggulu tiktaka kashaya- 20 ml bd before food for 15 days
- Malathyadi kera taila³ for external application
- Narasimha rasayana⁴ 1tsp at night with milk for 2 months.
- Triphala choorna and loha bhasma lepa for external application twice a week for 3 months.

DISCUSSION

According to Acharya Sushruta, Pitta along with Vata getting localized at the roots of hair follicles causes hair fall and thereafter Kapha along with Rakta obstructs the channel of these hair follicles leading to cessation of regrowth of hair over that area and this condition is known as Indralupta. Thus derangements of Vata, Pitta, Kapha and Rakta are the main causative factors of Indralupta. While describing the disorders occurring due to over indulgence in Katu, Lavana, Snigdha and Viruddha ahara, acharyas have mentioned hair loss. It has also been mentioned that excessive intake of Lavana, Katu also causes Khalitya. Thus, it can be said that a person habituated to excessive Lavana or Kshara intake and taking Viruddha Ahara in routine, is prone to develop Indralupta. In the present case, the patient had the history of excessive intake of spicy, oily food, junk food. These processed foods may be acting as Virudha Ahara. This might have caused vitiation of Pitta Dosha in the patient and caused the problem of patchy hair loss. The patient was complaining of lack of appetite which indicates Agnimandya causing improper digestion of ingested food.

During the process of digestion along with the formation of seven Dhatu of the body there is also formation of Upadhatu and Mala.

One of the waste product of Asthi Dhatu is Kेशha.⁵ When there is improper metabolism there will be no formation of proper Sara or Kitta. Low digestive fire is a major factor which affects normal metabolism in the body.

Thus, in the present case, low digestive capacity and impaired metabolism affecting the level of both micro and macro nutrients of the body might have affected the hair growth causing hair loss due to Vata and Pitta Dosha. Thus to correct the agni, chitrakadi vati has been given.

Pracchana karma was selected as raktamokshana as it is ideal chikitsa for rakta dushti.

Pracchana karma removes vitiated rakta and pitta and also avarana of kapha.

Ichhabhedhi Rasa contain Shunti, Maricha, Shuddha Parada, Shuddha Gandhaka, Tankana Bhasma and Shuddha Jayapala, which are having Tikshna, Ushna qualities.

Irritation caused by the corrosive effect of Jayapala manifest eruptions over the patchy area. When applied locally over the patch of hair loss, it might have increased the blood supply over the area and stimulated hair growth.

Arogyavardhini rasa is having avaranahara and rasayana properties, which may be useful to correct the underline pathology of disease.

All the ingredients of malathyadi taila are ushna and teekshna in nature. Ushna guna exhibits pachana of localised dosha and teekshna induces shodhana of accumulated dosha. Hence the remnants of srothorodha of kapha dosha at roma koopa may have been minimised with the local effect.

Guggulu tiktaka kashaya is indicated in sandhi asthi majja gata roga and is useful for all urdwajatrugata vikaras.

Triphala choorna and loha bhasma are keshya, helps in further regrowth of hair.

CONCLUSION

The present case study shows the efficacy of pracchana in the management of indralupta along with internal medications.

The drugs helped in regrowth of hairs, improving the blood circulation over the hair roots and providing a favourable condition for hair growth.

On this basis, it can be concluded that Ayurveda has great approach in curing the Indralupta.

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Figure:

Before treatment

After treatment

